

PICKLEBALL SPORT SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGIES: THE PHILIPPINE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS CONTEXT

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Abstract

Pickleball sports which is considered as an innovative sport, described as a combination of ping-pong, tennis, and badminton, and is considered a popular racquet sport played by individuals of all ages has a great acceptance level from the PE teachers and PE students in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines. However, it is unknown if these HEIs are able to sustain the sport within their institutions, thus, this study is conducted to determine the strategies in sustaining and propagating the sport. This research drew on the same set of respondents (N = 30 PE_{teachers}, N = 280 PE_{students}) from the determination of acceptance level. The profile variables of the two groups are determined, to measure the strategies to sustain the sports, weighted means are assessed using a 4-point Likert scale, analysis of variances was done to test differences using the weighted means as based scores, with profile variables as factors. The mean analyses showed that both PE teachers and students assessed strongly agree the strategies to sustain the sport in terms of curriculum inclusion, involvement opportunities, sports commitment, and leisure satisfaction. The test of variances showed that PE students' strategies to sustainability in terms of curriculum inclusion are statistically significantly varies with their (gender, ages, and readiness), involvement opportunities varies with their (gender and readiness), sports commitment varies with their (age and readiness), and leisure satisfaction varies with their readiness. However, the PE teachers' strategies to sustain was linked to sports commitment that statistically significantly varies with their ages. The following findings highlight that pickleball sport's players and enthusiasts can propagate the sport within their institutions.

Keywords: Pickleball Sport's Sustainability, Curriculum Development, PATHFit 3, HEIs, BPEd Program.

INTRODUCTION

Pickleball sports was already introduced in the Philippines in 2018 and in 2019, the sport was initially introduced to the different Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Luzon including the Department of Physical Education of President Ramon Magsaysay State University (PRMSU). The sport has a great acceptance level of these HEIs' PE teachers and PE students who are the recipients of the Pickleball Sport seminars and workshops conducted, because these HEIs are offering a degree program of Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd) under their respective College of Education. Apart from the BPEd program, the physical education (PE) courses such as PE1 (fitness and recreational outdoor activities), PE2 (Philippine folkdance), PathFit 3 (physical activities toward health and fitness), and PE4 (team sports) are mandated, as part of the general education courses that need to be taken and passed by the students to earn a bachelor's degree of their choice other than the BPEd program. However, despite of this high acceptance level, the sustainability and propagation of the sport is still an assumption and unknown as to what strategies would these HEIs will implement, therefore, the purpose of conducting this follow up study is to investigate the different strategies that would sustain and propagate the sport in the Philippines.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to investigate the strategies to sustain and propagate the Pickleball sport, being a new and innovative sport in the Philippines after showing a high acceptance level from the selected HEIs, both public and private, in Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao, where it has been already introduced.

Specifically, this study was conducted with the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of the two groups of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Gender,
 - 1.2 Age,
 - 1.3 Sports engage, and
 - 1.4 Readiness to adapt to the new sport?
2. What is the assessment of the respondents on the sustainability strategies of the Pickleball as the new sport in the Philippines in terms of:
 - 2.1 Curriculum Inclusion,
 - 2.2 Involvement Opportunities,
 - 2.3 Sports Commitment, and
 - 2.4 Leisure Satisfaction?
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the sustainability strategies of pickleball sport when they are grouped according to their profile variables?
4. What sustainability program may be proposed based on the results and findings of the study?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sustainability Strategies of Pickleball Sport

Pickleball being an emerging sport that has fewer participants than other popular sports, a group of pickleball enthusiasts who are involved in the sport, and trying to energize the pickleball community which could serve as a catalyst for the promotion of pickleball in other countries, that is to propagate the sport and be played by all age groups. Unlike other competitive sports, pickleball is easy to pick up and requires simple equipment. Wray et al., (2021) argued that pickleball is very accessible due to its economical and portable equipment, and can be played on a hard and flat surface of any size.

Furthermore, promoting the sports through establishment of tournaments popularizes the sports among the public, which leads to promoting it into a national sport (Chen, Ma, Yu, and Chiu, 2021). Additionally, the Philippine Pickleball Association has its organization direction for the Pickleball sport sustainability such as inclusion of the sport to school's curriculum;

involvement opportunities with partner institutions and community to create their own groups or clubs or association; committed to developing the grassroots, coaching, and officiating programs; and leisure satisfaction of players while playing the sports.

Curriculum Inclusion

Curriculum is the rational conversation between learner and coursework in higher education. It is the students' experience, on any given campus, of any given course; each syllabus represents one sequential or supporting piece of evidence that students have indeed engaged the institution. The CHED is a government agency that governed the tertiary level of education in the Philippines that oversees HEIs, such as colleges and universities, both public and private. There were over 2,396 HEIs in the country which can be divided into public and private institutions, of the figure, 667 were public HEIs which account for 27.84% of all HEIs, while 1,729 were private institutions account for 72.16% of all HEIs (CHED Statistics, 2020).

These HEIs were offering a degree program of BPEd under their respective College of Education. Apart from the BPEd program, the physical education (PE) subjects such as PE1 (fitness and recreational outdoor activities), PE2 (Philippine folkdance), PE3 (Individual and Dual Sports), and PE4 (team sports) subjects are mandated, as part of the general education subjects that need to be taken and passed by the students to earn a bachelor's degree of their choice other than the BPEd program.

Therefore, pickleball sport can be incorporated and taught in PE 3 general education subject, not just in BPEd program but in other bachelor's degree programs as well, provided that the new and innovative pickleball sport is accepted by the HEIs for implementation without the need for CHED approval, but a discretion to PE teachers and the school. The inclusion of the new sport in the curriculum is a way also to sustain the sport's acceptability.

A university in Central Luzon already had included the pickleball sport in their curriculum specifically in PE 3 general subject and in Individual-Dual Sports (Major 7 subject) of the BPEd program as well. In addition, James (2019) averred that effectively teaching pickleball skills in physical education could lead to a lifelong participation in pickleball, as well as the possible transfer of skills to more complex racquet sports.

Involvement Opportunities

The involvement of sport enthusiasts is the key to the success and long term sustainability of sports, sport clubs, sport organizations, and sport events. Without them, the sport system could not operate and propagate. According to the theory of Scanlan, Carpenter, Schmidt, Simons, and Keeler (1993), involvement opportunities are valued opportunities that are present only through continued sport involvement. It further states that being committed to sport will be influenced by the opportunities that the participant can receive as a result of participation within the activity. The positive sign associated with this component of the model indicates that as the number and significance of involvement opportunities increases, sport commitment will increase.

According to Scanlan et al., (2003, 2009, 2013) opportunities in sport may include travel, job opportunities, performance recognition, friendships, and competitive achievement. The involvement in sport pickleball offers opportunities to players and coaches in the sense that this emerging sport has been played across the country, and therefore, sports enthusiasts and clubs may organize tournaments on their community.

Sports Commitment

According to Scanlan, Chow, Sousa, Scanlan, and Knifsend (2015), Sport Commitment is the psychological state to persist in a sport over time. It was suggested by Brickman (1987) that the nature of commitment includes a functional component as well as an obligatory component. In other words, individuals can persist in an endeavor because they “want to” and because they “have to.” Commitment in the sport context has been conceptualized and measured at various levels including commitment to a program (Scanlan, Simons et al., 1993), to a team (Scanlan et al., 2003, 2013), or to a specific sport (Weiss, Weiss, & Amorose, 2010). Furthermore, Scanlan et al., (2015) indicate that playing pickleball improves the player’s perception of their overall well-being and quality of life even in the presence of increased injury incidence. Therefore, it should be considered that although playing pickleball is a risky activity, this risk may be outweighed by the benefits of active play resulting in the overall well-being and quality of life of the pickleball player.

Leisure Satisfaction

The process of playing pickleball generates many subjective personal feelings that affect the players’ emotions or perceptions of life, thus, giving rise to the issue of well-being (Keung and Goswami, 2011). The more pickleball participants are involved in pickleball, the higher their leisure benefits; for instance, Heo, Ryu, Yang, Kim, and Rhee (2018) pointed out that playing pickleball as a form of serious leisure may add significant value to the individual’s daily lives and contribute to successful aging, thus, pickleball plays an important role for players to obtain benefits. Additionally, as they invest far more time, equipment, and energy than people who regard pickleball as an ordinary leisure activity, participants of pickleball tournaments are different from general participants, thus, they should pay more attention to their leisure satisfaction.

Also, a study revealed that commitment to serious leisure is associated with lower levels of depression (Heo, Ryu, Yang, & Kim, 2018); the higher involvement in pickleball, the higher their leisure benefits which may add significant value to people’s daily lives and contribute to successful aging (Heo, Ryu, Yang, Kim, and Rhee, 2018); thus, pickleball plays an important role for participants to obtain leisure satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive comparative design to determine the strategies implemented from the selected public and private HEIs from Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao to sustain and propagate the pickleball as a new sport in the Philippines; comparing the findings between the PE teachers and PE students about the pickleball sport’s sustainability strategies.

The descriptive statistics pertained to the profile variables of the two groups of respondents, the PE teachers and PE students; the mean analyzed the sustainability strategies, guided by the 4-point Likert scale as 4=Strongly Agree to 1- Strongly Disagree. Inferential statistics such as Analysis of Variances was also done to compare the means to determine if any statistical differences exist, Reject the null hypothesis if p- value ≤ 0.05 and Accept the null hypothesis if p- value ≥ 0.05 .

This research drew on the same set of respondents (N = 30 PEteachers, N = 280 PEstudents) from the determination of acceptance level, from the selected public and private HEIs in Luzon, Visayas, and Mindanao, a total of 310 respondents. The respondents were selected through multistage sampling. The two groups of respondents were divided into clusters based on geographic such as island, then HEIs. After clustering, the respondents were randomly selected obtaining the sample size of 30 PE teachers and 280 PE students. This method was conducted among the HEIs of the three geographic islands in the country. Randomization was employed so that each respondent within each cluster is a representative of the total respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Profile Variables of the Respondents

Table 1: Profile Variables of the Respondents

		PE Teachers		PE Students	
		Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	19	63.33	64	22.86
	Female	11	36.67	195	69.64
	LGBTQ+			21	7.50
	Total	30	100.00	280	100.00
Age	15-19 years old			95	33.93
	20-24 years old			179	63.93
	25-29 years old	6	20.00	3	1.07
	30-34 years old	5	16.67	3	1.07
	35-39 years old	8	26.67		
	45-49 years old	4	13.33		
	50-54 years old	4	13.33		
	55-59 years old	2	6.67		
	60-64 years old	1	3.33		
Total	30	100.00	280	100.00	
Sports Engaged In	Table tennis	1	3.33	19	6.79
	Tennis			14	5.00
	Badminton	9	30.00	85	30.36
	Others	20	66.67	162	57.86
	Total	30	100.00	280	100.00
Readiness to adapt the new sports	Yes	30	100.00	266	95.00
	No			14	5.00
	Total	30	100.00	280	100.00

The results show that majority of the PE teachers are male with 19 or 63.33%, while the majority of the PE students are female with 195 or 69.64%.

Majority of the PE teachers' age range from 35-39 years old with 8 or 26.67, while the majority of the PE students' age is from 20-24 years old with 179 or 63.93%.

Majority of the PE teachers and PE students are engaged in other sports rather than racket sports with 20 or 66.67%, and with 162 or 57.86%.

Both PE teachers and PE students are ready to adapt the new sports with 30 or 100%, and with 266 or 95%.

2. Respondent's Assessment on the Sustainability Strategies of the Pickleball Sport

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis on the Respondent's Assessment on the Sustainability of Pickleball Sport in terms of Curriculum Inclusion

Curriculum Inclusion	PE Teachers				PE Students			
	Mean	SD	QI	Rank	Mean	SD	QI	Rank
1. Include in the course/subject contents of the PE and Sports-related curriculum, both general subject and major courses	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	6.5	3.43	0.52	Strongly Agree	1
2. Teach pickleball in PE3/Path-Fit 3 general education course	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	4	3.39	0.52	Strongly Agree	5.5
3. Include pickleball in Individual-Dual Sports course in the BPEd program	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	6.5	3.39	0.56	Strongly Agree	5.5
4. Organize pickleball sport seminars and workshops as part of the culminating activity of the BPEd students	4.00	0.00	Strongly Agree	1	3.41	0.56	Strongly Agree	2
5. Apply the basic skills of the pickleball during the class as part of the course discussion	3.97	0.18	Strongly Agree	2	3.40	0.60	Strongly Agree	3.5
6. Develop pickleball learning module and utilization	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	4	3.40	0.60	Strongly Agree	3.5
7. Organize college and school-wide mini-tournament	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	4	3.37	0.57	Strongly Agree	7
Overall Weighted Mean	3.94	0.22	Strongly Agree		3.40	0.56	Strongly Agree	

Table 2 shows that the PE teachers and PE students strongly agree on the curriculum inclusion of the pickleball sport for sustainability with an overall weighted mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers} = 3.94$; $\sigma = 0.22$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students} = 3.40$; $\sigma = 0.56$), respectively. Moreover, the PE teachers also strongly agree in all the statement indicators to "Organize pickleball sport seminars and workshops as part of the culminating activity of the BPEd students" with the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers} = 4.00$; $\sigma = 0.00$) ranks 1st. They likewise strongly agree on the "Inclusion in the course/subject contents

of the PE and Sports-related curriculum, both general subject and major courses” and to “Include pickleball in Individual-Dual Sports course in the BPEd program” with the lowest means ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}= 3.90$; $\sigma=0.31$) last in rank, respectively.

On the other hand, the PE students similarly strongly agree in all statement indicators, wherein the “Inclusion in the course/subject contents of the PE and Sports-related curriculum, both general subject and major courses” with the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.43$; $\sigma=0.52$) ranks 1st; as well as, they strongly agree to “Organize college and school-wide mini-tournament” with the lowest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}= 3.37$; $\sigma=0.57$) ranks 7th.

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis on the Respondent’s Assessment on the Sustainability of Pickleball Sport in terms of Involvement Opportunities

Involvement Opportunities	PE Teachers				PE Students			
	Mean	SD	QI	Rank	Mean	SD	QI	Rank
1. Travel to other places when conducting clinics in communities	3.77	0.43	Strongly Agree	7	3.33	0.60	Strongly Agree	7
2. Meet different sports enthusiasts	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	3.5	3.50	0.58	Strongly Agree	2
3. Performance recognition	3.83	0.46	Strongly Agree	6	3.49	0.59	Strongly Agree	3.5
4. Offer the opportunity for both players and coaches to travel to different places across the country for competition.	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	3.5	3.48	0.61	Strongly Agree	5
5. Sports enthusiasts and clubs may organize tournaments in their community and develop grassroots players	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	3.5	3.46	0.57	Strongly Agree	6
6. Participate in Pickleball Tournament will give participant a sense of achievement	3.97	0.18	Strongly Agree	1	3.56	0.56	Strongly Agree	1
7. Participate in Pickleball Tournament will help participant broaden their knowledge	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	3.5	3.49	0.58	Strongly Agree	3.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.90	0.30	Strongly Agree		3.47	0.58	Strongly Agree	

Table 3 shows that the PE teachers and PE students strongly agree on the involvement opportunity of the pickleball sports for sustainability with an overall weighted mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.90$; $\sigma=0.30$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.47$; $\sigma=0.58$), respectively.

Also, the PE teachers and the PE students strongly agree in all the statement indicators to wherein “Participating in Pickleball Tournament will give participant a sense of achievement” with the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.97$; $\sigma=0.18$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}= 3.56$; $\sigma=0.56$) both 1st in rank. The PE teachers and the PE students likewise strongly agree that “Travel to other places when conducting clinics in communities” can sustains the new sports with the lowest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.77$; $\sigma=0.43$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.33$; $\sigma=0.60$) both ranks 7th.

Table 4: Descriptive Analysis on the Respondent’s Assessment on the Sustainability of Pickleball Sport in terms of Sports Commitment

Sports Commitment	PE Teachers				PE Students			
	Mean	SD	QI	Rank	Mean	SD	QI	Rank
1. Play pickleball during class vacant/break	3.67	0.55	Strongly Agree	7	3.26	0.61	Strongly Agree	7
2. Introduce pickleball to others whenever I have the opportunity	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	2	3.40	0.63	Strongly Agree	4.5
3. Participate in Pickleball could help individual realize their ideals	3.83	0.38	Strongly Agree	5	3.40	0.61	Strongly Agree	4.5
4. This sports activity is an important reflection of who I am	3.70	0.47	Strongly Agree	6	3.27	0.67	Strongly Agree	6
5. Enjoy playing this sport activity	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	3	3.42	0.59	Strongly Agree	3
6. This sports activity allows players to improve their health and fitness.	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	1	3.46	0.59	Strongly Agree	1.5
7. Have social interactions with others by participating in a pickleball activity	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	4	3.46	0.63	Strongly Agree	1.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.83	0.37	Strongly Agree		3.38	0.62	Strongly Agree	

Table 4 shows that the PE teachers and PE students strongly agree as well on the sports commitment of the pickleball sports for sustainability with an overall weighted means ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.83$; $\sigma=0.37$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.38$; $\sigma=0.62$), respectively.

The PE teachers and the PE students also strongly agree in all statement indicators wherein “This sports activity allows players to improve their health and fitness” with the highest means ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.93$; $\sigma=0.25$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.46$; $\sigma=0.59$); as well as, “Having social interactions with others by participating in a pickleball activity” similarly has the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.46$; $\sigma=0.63$) both 1st in rank. On the other hand, the PE teachers and the PE students likewise strongly agree that “Playing pickleball during class vacant/break” sustained the new sports with the lowest means ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.67$; $\sigma=0.55$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.26$; $\sigma=0.61$) both ranks 7th.

Table 5: Descriptive Analysis on the Respondent’s Assessment on the Sustainability of Pickleball Sport in terms of Leisure Satisfaction

Leisure Satisfaction	PE Teachers				PE Students			
	Mean	SD	QI	Rank	Mean	SD	QI	Rank
1. Playing pickleball generates personal feelings that positively affect the players’ well-being	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	4	3.46	0.53	Strongly Agree	1
2. Playing pickleball may add significant value to the individual’s daily life and contribute to successful aging	3.93	0.25	Strongly Agree	2	3.40	0.54	Strongly Agree	5
3. Pickleball plays a vital role for players to obtain benefits	3.97	0.18	Strongly Agree	1	3.44	0.54	Strongly Agree	2.5
4. Playing pickleball is associated with lower levels of depression	3.80	0.41	Strongly Agree	7	3.33	0.61	Strongly Agree	7
5. The sport is the most enjoyable of all leisure activities	3.83	0.46	Strongly Agree	6	3.37	0.62	Strongly Agree	6
6. Participating in pickleball activities allows players to express themselves	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	4	3.44	0.59	Strongly Agree	2.5
7. Pickleball is one of the activities that players felt most satisfied – creating a unique image of self	3.90	0.31	Strongly Agree	4	3.43	0.54	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.89	0.32	Strongly Agree		3.41	0.57	Strongly Agree	

Table 5 shows that the PE teachers and PE students strongly agree on the leisure satisfaction of the pickleball sports for sustainability with an overall weighted mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.89$; $\sigma=0.32$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.41$; $\sigma=0.57$), respectively.

The PE teachers and the PE students likewise strongly agree in all statement indicators wherein, “Pickleball plays a vital role for players to obtain benefits” with the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.97$; $\sigma=0.18$), and the “Playing pickleball generates personal feelings that positively affect the players’ well-being” with the highest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.46$; $\sigma=0.53$) both 1st in rank, can sustain the new sports. On the other hand, the two group of respondents strongly agree that “Playing pickleball is associated with lower levels of depression” with the lowest mean ($\bar{X}_{PE\ teachers}=3.80$; $\sigma=0.41$) and ($\bar{X}_{PE\ students}=3.33$; $\sigma=0.61$) both ranks 7th, respectively.

3. Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of the Respondent's on the Sustainability Strategies of the Pickleball Sports according to their Profile Variables

Table 6: Difference on the Respondent's Assessment of Pickleball Sport's Sustainability in terms of Curriculum Inclusion as to Profile Variables

Sources of Variation	PE Teachers			PE Students		
	F	p-value	Decision	F	p-value	Decision
Gender	.007	.932	Accept Ho Not Significant	4.253	.015	Reject Ho Significant
Age	.724	.736	Accept Ho Not Significant	2.609	.003	Reject Ho Significant
Sports Engage	.160	.853	Accept Ho Not Significant	2.209	.087	Accept Ho Not Significant
Readiness to adapt the new sport	There are fewer than two groups for dependent variable curriculum. No statistics are computed.			9.892	.002	Reject Ho Significant

Results are based on One-Way ANOVA, $\alpha=0.05$, $df_{PE\ teacher}=29$, $df_{PE\ Students}=279$. Reject null hypothesis if $p<0.05$

Table 6 shows the test values of PE teachers and PE students. The PE teachers' computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.632$), age ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.736$), and sports engage ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.853$) are greater than $>$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, therefore, there is no significant difference on the PE teachers' assessment of pickleball sports' sustainability through curriculum inclusion based on their profile variables.

On the other hand, the PE students' computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.015$), age ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.003$), and readiness to adapt the new sports ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.002$) are less than $<$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is a significant difference on the PE students' assessment of pickleball sports' sustainability through curriculum inclusion based on their gender, age, and readiness to adapt.

Table 7: Difference on the Respondent's Assessment of Pickleball Sport's Sustainability in terms of Involvement Opportunities as to Profile Variables

Sources of Variation	PE Teachers			PE Students		
	F	p-value	Decision	F	p-value	Decision
Gender	.512	.480	Accept Ho Not Significant	5.385	.005	Reject Ho Significant
Age	2.287	.075	Accept Ho Not Significant	1.218	.270	Accept Ho Not Significant
Sports Engage	.357	.703	Accept Ho Not Significant	2.209	.087	Accept Ho Not Significant
Readiness to adapt the new sport	There are fewer than two groups for dependent variable involvement. No statistics are computed			10.122	.002	Reject Ho Significant

Results are based on One-Way ANOVA, $\alpha=0.05$, $df_{PE\ teacher}=29$, $df_{PE\ Students}=279$. Reject null hypothesis if $p<0.05$

Table 7 shows the test values of PE teachers and PE students. The PE teachers’ computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.480$), age ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.075$), and sports engage ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.703$) are greater than $>$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, therefore, there is no significant difference on the PE teachers’ assessment of pickleball sport’s sustainability through involvement opportunities based on their profile variables.

On the other hand, the PE students’ computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.005$) and readiness to adapt the new sports ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.002$) are less than $<$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is a significant difference on the PE students’ assessment of pickleball sport’s sustainability through involvement opportunities based on their gender and readiness to adapt.

Table 8: Difference on the Respondent’ Assessment of Pickleball Sport’s Sustainability in terms of Sports Commitment as to Profile Variables

Sources of Variation	PE Teachers			PE Students		
	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Gender	.161	.691	Accept Ho Not Significant	2.708	.068	Accept Ho Not Significant
Age	3.513	.016	Reject Ho Significant	2.662	.002	Reject Ho Significant
Sports Engage	.703	.504	Accept Ho Not Significant	1.873	.134	Accept Ho Not Significant
Readiness to adapt the new sports	<i>There are fewer than two groups for dependent variable commitment. No statistics are computed</i>			11.210	.001	Reject Ho Significant

Results are based on One-Way ANOVA, $\alpha=0.05$, $df_{PE\ teacher}=29$, $df_{PE\ Students}=279$. Reject null hypothesis if $p<0.05$

Table 8 shows the test values of PE teachers and PE students. The two groups of respondents’ computed value for age ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.016$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.002$) and readiness to adapt the new sports ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.001$) are less than $<$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is a significant difference on the respondents’ assessment of pickleball sports’ sustainability in terms of sports commitment based on their age; and in terms of PE student’s sports commitment based on their readiness to adapt.

On the other hand, the respondents’ computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.691$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.068$) and sports engage ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.504$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.134$) are greater than $>$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, therefore, there is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessment of pickleball sports’ sustainability through sports commitment based on their gender and sports engage.

Table 9: Difference on the Respondent’ Assessment of Pickleball Sport’s Sustainability in terms of Leisure Satisfaction as to Profile Variables

Source of Variation	PE Teachers			PE Students		
	F	p-value	Decision	F	p-value	Decision
Gender	.019	.891	Accept Ho Not Significant	1.345	.262	Accept Ho Not Significant
Age	2.574	.051	Accept Ho Not Significant	1.582	.096	Accept Ho Not Significant
Sports Engage	.238	.790	Accept Ho Not Significant	2.322	.075	Accept Ho Not Significant
Readiness to adapt the new sports	<i>There are fewer than two groups for dependent variable leisure. No statistics are computed.</i>			4.989	.026	Reject Ho Significant

Results are based on One-Way ANOVA, $\alpha=0.05$, $df_{PE\ teacher}=29$, $df_{PE\ Students}=279$. Reject null hypothesis if $p<0.05$

Table 9 shows the test values of PE teachers and PE students. The two groups of respondents’ computed value for gender ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.891$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.262$) age ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.051$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.096$) and sports engage ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ teachers}=0.790$; $p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.075$) are greater than $>$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, therefore, there is no significant difference on the respondents’ assessment of pickleball sport’s sustainability through leisure satisfaction based on their gender, age, and sports engage. On the other hand, the PE student’s computed value for readiness to adapt the new sports ($p\text{-value}_{PE\ students}=0.026$) is less than $<$ the 0.05 alpha level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is a significant difference on the PE student’s assessment of pickleball sports’ sustainability in terms of leisure satisfaction based on their readiness to adapt.

Proposed Plans/Programs for the Acceptability of Pickleball Sport

Plans/ Programs	Objectives	Key Result Area	Program Activities	Key Performance Indices	Performance Target	Key Personnel	Budgetary Requirement
Sustainability Plans/ Programs	Objective 1: To make pickleball be part of the Physical Education subjects	> Draft of the pickleball syllabus	> Crafting of the syllabus	> Percentage of physical education educators integrating the sports	> Developed syllabus for inclusion, recognized by the CHED	> Philippine Professional Pickleball Association (PPA); HEIs; CHED	>P20,000
		> Inclusion of the sports in the physical education curriculum	> Integration of the sports in the PATHFit 3 courses	> Percentage of target HEIs implementing the pickle inclusion in the curriculum	> Pickleball sports in the HEIs’ PATHFit 3 courses		
	Objective 2: To make pickleball be part of the sports tournament and in leisure sports	> Conduct of pickleball tournament > Be played in leisure activity, both in schools and in community	> Invitation letter to HEIs, LGUs, and sports association to participate in the tournament > Tap suppliers of racket, ball, and net	> Proposed pickleball tournament > Availability of equipment and facilities for leisure players	> The conduct of pickleball tournament of all ages > Direct supplier of the basic equipment and facilities, utilizing the online shops for products availability	> Philippine Professional Pickleball Association (PPA); HEIs; community, online platform	>P50,000

CONCLUSIONS

The following findings highlight that pickleball sport's players and enthusiasts can sustain and propagate the sport within their institutions. It may be adapted not just in the academe but also in sports associations and clubs around the country, that leads to grassroots development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given that the two groups of respondents are strongly agree on the strategies for sport's sustainability, BPEd program of HEIs are encouraged to incorporate the pickleball sport as part of their PathFit 3 courses. HEIs may adapt the syllabus developed for pickleball.

Course Syllabus Template

Course Name	Pickleball
Course Credits	2 / 3 Units
Course Description	<p>Pickleball is a paddle sport that combines elements of tennis, badminton, and ping-pong using a paddle and plastic ball with holes.</p> <p>This course aims to equip students with the knowledge of systematic and natural approaches to improve health, fitness and quality of life through active physical activities and recreation. It also emphasizes developing attitudes, self-discipline, and to maintain appropriate lifelong habits. This course will cover Pickleball catering on skills, rules, regulation, officiating and coaching.</p>
Contact Hours / Week	2 hours / week
Prerequisite	
Student-Instructor Ratio	35: 1
Course Outcomes	<p>At the end of the course, students will be able to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Demonstrate the ability to perform the correct fundamental skills in pickle ball. 2. Distinguish the fundamental skills, drills, routines, and strategies used in pickleball. 3. Engage in the different exercises and movement patterns using functional and sport specific skills for pickleball. 4. Show good values and exhibit just and fair judgment in coaching and officiating Pickleball. 5. Advocate engagement in physical activities through pickleball activities and events.

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